

AI-assisted CRISPR guide design vs.
traditional tools

AI-based vs. Rule-based CRISPR gRNA Design for β -thalassemia mutation

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Independent Computational Study

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Author Note

This work is an independent computational study conducted as a part of self-directed research and academic exploration.

Abstract

The β -globin gene (HBB) intronic mutation IVS-1-110 G>A disrupts normal pre-mRNA splicing, leading to reduced β -globin synthesis and β -thalassemia. In this study, the mutation was simulated in silico to evaluate CRISPR-Cas9 guide RNA (gRNA) design strategies using an artificial intelligence-based platform, CRISPRon (RTH), in comparison with traditional rule-based tools, Benchling and CHOPCHOP. gRNAs were prioritized based on proximity to the mutation site and predicted on-target efficiency, resulting in the selection of two candidates located within 13–15 bp of the variant. Cross-validation using CHOPCHOP and Benchling confirmed their cut-site positioning and comparable efficiency scores. Off-target assessment using Cas-OFFinder identified a single potential off-target site with one mismatch for each gRNA under conservative search conditions. These findings indicate that AI-assisted gRNA design can generate mutation-proximal and specific candidates, while highlighting the importance of integrating multiple computational tools and the necessity of experimental validation before therapeutic application.

Keywords: β -thalassemia; HBB IVS-1-110 G>A; CRISPR-Cas9; in silico; gRNA; off-target analysis

Introduction

Beta-thalassemia is an autosomal-recessive hematologic disorder characterized by deficient in β -globin synthesis, leading to reduced hemoglobin assembly within erythrocytes. Clinical severity spans a wide range, from the mild, often asymptomatic form (beta-thalassemia minor) to the severe, life-threatening form (beta-thalassemia major) that may require regular blood transfusions.

Beta-thalassemia is caused by mutations in the HBB gene leading to reduced or absent β -globin production. One of the most frequent mutations in Mediterranean and Asian populations is IVS-1-110 G>A in intron 1. This single-nucleotide substitution activates a complicated splice site, causing improper mRNA splicing. The abnormal transcript undergoes degradation or produces unstable protein, resulting in decreased β -globin levels and the clinical Thalassemia phenotype.

CRISPR-Cas9 technology offers the possibility to correct disease-causing mutations by inducing double-strand breaks near the target site. Designing highly specific and efficient gRNAs is crucial. Traditional design tools such as Benchling and CHOPCHOP rely on established rule-based algorithms. In contrast, CRISPRon (RTH) applies machine-learning trained on large experimental datasets, representing an AI-based approach. This study compares AI and non-AI-designed gRNAs targeting the HBB IVS-1-110 site, with in-silico validation of efficiency and off-target profiles.

Aim & Objectives

To design and validate CRISPR–Cas9 guides (gRNAs) targeting the HBB IVS-1-110 G>A β -thalassemia mutation using an AI–based tool (CRISPRon) and compare them with traditional gRNA design platforms (Benchling and CHOPCHOP) through in-silico analysis of efficiency, specificity, and feasibility.

Tools and Resources

- Databases & Sequences
 - RefSeq HBB gene sequence (NG_000007.3)
 - Transcript reference (NM_000518.5)
 - ClinVar database for mutation reference
- gRNA Design Tools
 - CRISPRon (RTH server): AI–based on–target efficiency prediction
 - Benchling: traditional online design platform
 - CHOPCHOP: rule–based guide design and visualization
- Validation & Analysis Tool
 - Cas–OFFinder (CRISPR RGEN Tools): mutation / off–target analysis

Methodology

Sequence preparation

The HBB gene sequence for Reference Sequence NC_000007.3 (the human beta-globin gene cluster) and NM_000518.5 (the beta subunit of hemoglobin) were obtained from NCBI database to compare and annotate exon-intron boundaries. Alignment of the two sequences enabled precise localization of intron 1 (in Fig. 1).

Here, the first exon starts from ACA from first line to CAG ending in third line (142 nt). The first intron starts after the exon from GTT....TAG (130 nt highlighted boldly).

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>NG_000007.3 HBB
ACATTTGCTTCTGCACAACTGTGTTCACTAGCAACCTCAAACAGACACCCATGGTGCATCTGACTCCTGA
GGAGAAGTCTGCCGTTACTGCCCTGTGGGGCAAGGTGAACGTGGATGAAAGTTGGTGTGAGGCCCTGGGC
AGGTTGGTATCAAGGTTACAAGACAGGTTAAGGAGACCAATAGAAACTGGGCATGTGGAGACAGAGAAG
ACTCTTGGGTTTCTGATAGGCACTGACTCTCTGCTATTGGTCTATTTCCACCCTTAGGCTGCTGG
TGGTCTACCCTTGGACCCAGAGGTTCTTTGAGTCCTTTGGGGATCTGTCCACTCCTGATGCTGTTATGGG
CAACCCTAAGGTGAAGGCTCATGGCAAGAAAGTGCTCGGTGCCTTTAGTGATGGCCTGGCTCACCTGGAC
AACCTCAAGGGCACCTTTGCCACACTGAGTGAGCTGCACTGTGACAAGCTGCACGTGGATCCTGAGAAGT
TCAGGGTGAGTCTATGGGACGCTTGATGTTTTCTTCCCTTCTTTTCTATGGTTAAGTTCATGTCATAG
GAAGGGGATAAGTAACAGGGTACAGTTTAGAATGGGAAACAGACGAATGATTGCATCAGTGTGGAAGTCT
CAGGATCGTTTTAGTTTCTTTATTTGCTGTTTATAACAATGTTTTCTTTTGTTAATTCTTGCTTTCT
TTTTTTTTCTTCCGCAATTTTACTATTATACTTAATGCCTTAACATTGTGTATAACAAAAGGAAATA
TCTCTGAGATACATTAAGTAACTTAAAAAAAACTTACACAGTCTGCCTAGTACATTACTATTTGGAAT
ATATGTGTGCTTATTTGCATATTCATAATCTCCCTACTTTATTTTCTTTTATTTTAAATTGATACATAAT
CATTATACATATTTATGGGTTAAAGTGAATGTTTTAATATGTGTACACATATTGACCAAATCAGGGTAA
TTTTGCATTTGTAATTTAAAAAATGCTTCTTCTTTAATATACTTTTTTGTATCTTATTCTAATA
CTTCCCTAATCTTTCTTTCAAGGCAATAATGATACAATGTATCATGCCTCTTTGCACCATTCTAAAG
AATAACAGTGATAATTTCTGGGTTAAGGCAATAGCAATATCTGTCATATAAATATTTCTGCATATAAAT
TGTAAGTGTGTAAGAGGTTTCATATTGCTAATAGCAGCTACAATCCAGCTACCATTCTGCTTTTATTTT
ATGGTTGGGATAAGGCTGGATTATTCTGAGTCCAAGCTAGGCCCTTTTGCTAATCATGTTTCATACCTCTT
ATCTTCTCCACAGCTCCTGGGCAACGTGCTGGTCTGTGTGCTGGCCATCACTTTGGCAAAGAATTCA
CCCCACAGTGCAGGCTGCCTATCAGAAAGTGGTGGCTGGTGTGGCTAATGCCCTGGCCACAAAGTATCA
CTAAGCTCGCTTTCTGCTGTCCAATTTCTATTAAGGTTCTTTGTTCCCTAAGTCCAACACTAAACT
GGGGGATATTATGAAGGGCCTTGGATCTGGATTCTGCCTAATAAAAAACATTTATTTTCATTGCAA
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Figure 1. HBB gene NG_000007.3 FASTA

The IVS-1-110 G>A mutation was introduced by substituting guanine with adenine at the 110th nucleotide position of the intron 1.

gRNA Design

After simulating the mutation in silico, the genomic region spanning 200 base pairs upstream and 200 base pairs downstream of the mutation site was extracted in FASTA format. This 400–bp sequence was submitted to CRISPRon, CHOPCHOP, and Benchling to predict and compare high–efficiency guide RNAs, allowing cross–validation of gRNA candidates based on on–target activity and design parameters.

AI-based design: CRISPRon (RTH) was used to generate candidate gRNAs.

Figure 2. CRISPRon Predictions for gRNA (in Blue, Green bands)

From the predicted guide RNA candidates, only targets exhibiting an efficiency score of $\geq 50\%$ were shortlisted for further evaluation. Among these, two gRNAs, designated *m_210* and *m_211*, were selected based on a combination of high predicted efficiency and close spatial proximity to the mutation site, located approximately 13–15 bp away.

In this selection process, proximity to the mutation was given higher priority, as guides positioned closer to the target site are generally more favorable for precise genome editing outcomes.

Choose which targets to show in the browser above and table below

All targets
 Targets with efficiency >= 50% and not repeat sequence
 Targets with efficiency >= 50% for which off-targets have been obtained
[Download](#) guides currently shown in table.

id	target+PAM	region	genome	specificity	Eff.(%)	cut-site
<input type="checkbox"/> p_40	CCTGTGGGGCAAGGTGAACGTGG	40:+	5226958:-	Unknown	69	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_53	GTGAACGTGGATGAAGTTGGTGG	53:+	5226945:-	Unknown	67	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_293	TATGGGCAACCCCTAAGGTGAAGG	293:+	5226705:-	Unknown	61	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_81	CCTGATACCAACCTGCCCAAGGG	81:-	5226917:+	Unknown	60	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_210	ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGGG	210:-	5226788*:+	Unknown	59	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_26	TCTGCCGTTACTGCCCTGTGGGG	26:+	5226972:-	Unknown	59	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_211	GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGG	211:-	5226787*:+	Unknown	58	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_262	AGGAGTGGACAGATCCCAAAGG	262:-	5226736:+	Unknown	57	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_118	TAAGGAGACCAATAGAACTGGG	118:+	5226880:-	Unknown	56	HBB:Intronic
<input type="checkbox"/> p_24	AGTCTGCCGTTACTGCCCTGTGG	24:+	5226974:-	Unknown	56	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_277	GCCCATAACGCATCAGGAGTGG	277:-	5226721:+	Unknown	55	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_229	TGGTCTACCCCTGGACCCAGAGG	229:+	5226769:-	Unknown	54	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_356	GGCTCACCTGGACAACCTCAAGG	356:+	5226642:-	Unknown	53	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_58	CGTGGATGAAGTTGGTGGTGAAGG	58:+	5226940:-	Unknown	51	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> m_14	GTAACGGCAGACTTCTCCTCAGG	14:-	5226984:+	Unknown	51	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_50	AAGGTGAACGTGGATGAAGTTGG	50:+	5226948:-	Unknown	50	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_125	ACCAATAGAAACTGGGCATGTGG	125:+	5226873:-	Unknown	50	HBB:Intronic
<input type="checkbox"/> p_73	TGGTGAGGCCCTGGCAGGTTGG	73:+	5226925:-	Unknown	50	HBB:CDS
<input type="checkbox"/> p_315	GCTCATGGCAAGAAAGTCTCGG	315:+	5226683:-	Unknown	50	HBB:CDS

Figure 3. CRISPRon designed gRNA list showing regions genomic positions and their efficiencies

Table 1

Selected CRISPRon-predicted gRNAs targeting the HBB IVS-1-110 G>A mutation

Id	Target + PAM	Region	Genome	Efficiency (%)
m_210	ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGGG	210: -	5226788: +	59
m_211	GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGG	211: -	5226787: +	58

Traditional design: **CHOPCHOP** and **Benchling** applications were used to identify guides in the same region using rule-based scoring.

CHOPCHOP

Figure 4. CHOPCHOP application showing list of gRNA designs for the mutated region (in 200th position)

The same 400-bp FASTA sequence was submitted to the CHOPCHOP application, which generated a list of candidate gRNAs. From this output, two gRNAs (**Rank 43** and **Rank 28**) were selected by first prioritizing their proximity to the mutation site and subsequently considering their predicted efficiency scores. Notably, the gRNAs selected in CHOPCHOP were completely identical to those obtained from the CRISPRon analysis, providing cross-tool validation of the selected guides.

Figure 5a. CHOPCHOP Application showing highlighted 'Rank 43' gRNA (identical to m_210)

Figure 5b. CHOPCHOP Application showing details and location of the 'Rank 43' gRNA

Figure 6a. CHOPCHOP Application showing highlighted 'Rank 28' gRNA (identical to m_211)

Figure 6b. CHOPCHOP Application showing details and location of the ‘Rank 28’ gRNA

Table 2

Selected CHOPCHOP–predicted gRNAs targeting the HBB IVS-1-110 G>A mutation

Id	Target + PAM	Location	Genome	Efficiency (%)
Rank43	ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGGG	210	5226788: Chr11	67.28
Rank28	GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGG	211	5226787: Chr 11	59.26

The predicted efficiencies of these gRNAs differed slightly in the CHOPCHOP application, reflecting the fact that individual gRNA design platforms rely on their own scoring criteria and computational approaches to estimate guide performance.

Benchling

Using the Benchling application, the same 400–bp FASTA sequence was once again submitted for gRNA prediction. This analysis identified gRNAs corresponding to *m_210* and *m_211*, consistent with those obtained from CRISPRon and CHOPCHOP.

Figure 7. Benchling application showing gRNA exactly like *m_210* gRNA

Figure 8. Benchling application showing gRNA exactly like *m_211* gRNA

Table 3

Selected Benchling–predicted gRNAs targeting the HBB IVS-1-110 G>A mutation

Id	Target + PAM	Location	On-target (%)	Off-Target (%)
1	ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGGG	216	67.3	55.1
2	GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTGG	217	59.3	62.7

These candidate guides were evaluated for their predicted efficiencies as well as their distances from the mutation site. The gRNAs selected through Benchling exhibited acceptable predicted on–target activity and were positioned near the mutation. While Benchling offers primary estimates of efficiency and specificity, a more thorough assessment of potential off–target effects was required.

Off-Target and Mismatch Verification using Cas-OFFinder

Cas-OFFinder was used to further evaluate the off-target potential of the selected gRNAs by allowing up to one nucleotide mismatch without permitting DNA or RNA bulges.

The screenshot shows the Cas-OFFinder interface for gRNA 'm_210'. The 'Summary' table indicates one found target with a bulge size of 0 and one mismatch. The 'Details' table provides the target sequence, chromosome (chr11), position (5226787), direction (+), and one mismatch.

Target Sequence	Bulge Type	Bulge Size	Mismatch	Number of Found Targets
ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTNGG	X	0	1	1

Bulge Type	Target	Chromosome	Position	Direction	Mismatches	Bulge Size
X	crRNA: ACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGTNGG DNA: ACCACCAGCAGCcTAAAGGGTGGG	chr11	5226787	+	1	0

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Figure 9. Cas-OFFinder analysis of gRNA ‘m_210’ showing one potential off-target site with a single nucleotide mismatch and no DNA or RNA bulge.

The screenshot shows the Cas-OFFinder interface for gRNA 'm_211'. The 'Summary' table indicates one found target with a bulge size of 0 and one mismatch. The 'Details' table provides the target sequence, chromosome (chr11), position (5226786), direction (+), and one mismatch.

Target Sequence	Bulge Type	Bulge Size	Mismatch	Number of Found Targets
GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGNGG	X	0	1	1

Bulge Type	Target	Chromosome	Position	Direction	Mismatches	Bulge Size
X	crRNA: GACCACCAGCAGCTTAAGGGNGG DNA: GACCACCAGCAGCcTAAAGGGTGG	chr11	5226786	+	1	0

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Figure 10. Cas-OFFinder analysis of gRNA ‘m_211’ identifying one potential off-target site with a single mismatch and no bulge formation.

For each gRNA, a single potential off-target site with one mismatch was identified, while no additional sites were detected under restrictive search conditions. When the mismatch tolerance was increased, additional theoretical off-target sites were observed, which is expected due to reduced specificity in the search parameters. These results indicate that the selected gRNAs exhibit high sequence specificity near the target region; however, experimental validation would be required to confirm off-target activity in a biological system.

Discussion

The HBB IVS-1-110 G>A mutation is a well-characterized pathogenic variant associated with β -thalassemia, as documented in clinical variant databases.

The classification of this variant as pathogenic or likely pathogenic highlights its biological and clinical significance. In this study, gRNAs were designed near this mutation to maximize relevance for potential genome editing strategies targeting abnormal splicing. The convergence of AI-based and traditional rule-based design tools on the same mutation-proximal gRNAs suggest a level of robustness and reliability in the in-silico guide selection process. Importantly, this agreement indicates that machine-learning-based tools may complement established algorithms rather than replace them. While the selected gRNAs demonstrated favorable predicted specificity and efficiency, this analysis remains computational in nature. Therefore, the functional impact of these guides on splicing correction and off-target activity would require experimental validation in appropriate cellular models before any therapeutic relevance can be inferred.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates an in-silico comparison of AI-based and traditional rule-based CRISPR gRNA design tools targeting the HBB IVS-I-110 G>A β -thalassemia mutation. The results show that gRNAs which were prioritized primarily by their proximity to the pathogenic mutation site, and secondarily by predicted on-target efficiency, were consistently identified across CRISPRon, Benchling, and CHOPCHOP. This prioritization strategy is particularly important for intronic splice-altering mutations, where precise targeting close to the mutation is critical to maximize corrective potential while minimizing unintended disruption of surrounding regulatory or intronic sequences. Emphasizing proximity also supports the goal of reducing collateral genomic damage, as it may lower the risk of undesired functional consequences elsewhere in the gene. Off-target analysis using Cas-OFFinder further supported the specificity of the selected guides under conservative search conditions. Overall, this work highlights the value of integrating multiple computational tools with biologically informed selection criteria for rational gRNA design, while highlighting the need for experimental validation prior to therapeutic application.

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